

Globalisation and Digitisation - The Exponential Spread of Infectious Information and its Possible Containment

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ABSTRACT

Wolfgang Sassin. *Globalization and Digitization - The Exponential Spread of Infectious Information and its Possible Containment* There is a fundamental difference between the human migration movements of the past and those of the beginning of the 21st century. The latter impose the need for a cultural assimilation of the migrants which they cannot master within one generation. This cultural transformation includes the necessity to adapt to the compression of humans into a new living space, into technology-based megapolises, which altogether represent the equivalent of an artificial planet. This new planet does not provide new resources nor additional free spaces for an overall growth of material wealth. On the contrary, it asks for a drastic reduction of individual freedoms. The stability, even the survival of these mega centres, is at stake without consistent subdivisions of an overall shrinking of spaces needed for all kinds of movements and of a consistent restriction of the exploding communicative interference within and between these mega centres. This essay aims at a first-hand analysis of a possible introduction of digital borders without which adequate legal spaces appear infeasible as the constituting framework of “our” artificial new planet.

Key words: humanity, legal space, digital ideological restriction, technological dominance, mega centre, individual freedom diminishing, migration, digital boundary, infection, infectious disease, COVID-19 social implications, coronavirus containment, globalisation, digitalisation, information, social immunity

CORONAVIRUS-PANDEMIC: HOW CAN WE EFFECTIVELY CONTROL SOCIAL CONTACTS AND MINIMIZE SOCIETAL IMPACT?

ACCORDING TO LEADING POLITICIANS, the unexpected appearance and rapid spread of the corona virus (Covid-19) poses a challenge to the affected societies that has not occurred since the end of the Second World War.²

If one considers that the measures taken in many countries to protect themselves from an exponentially growing wave of the disease date back to the time of the Second World War, then it becomes clear what long-term consequences the Black Swan Corona must have. The measures taken so far, and even those intensively discussed in the media, to contain Covid-19 concentrate on the physical and mental control of masses, because their potentially "dangerous" members cannot be identified sufficiently and quickly enough to isolate

² The messages of heads of government from many of the countries concerned were similar: On 18.3.2020 the German Chancellor Angela Merkel said: "It is serious. Take it seriously too. Since German unification, no, since the Second World War, there has not been a challenge to our country that depends so much on our joint solidarity."

them and then give them special treatment. The social and legal regulations of entire societies are therefore gradually being suspended and transformed into a kind of martial law. The real enemy is a „virus“, however. But the carriers of this virus spread the disaster. Only they and not the virus can be isolated. Therefore there is hope to make these carriers immune by a vaccination which is still to be developed. The actual "defensive battle" must therefore be fought in the individual carriers, who should and must maintain an existing social order.

In this respect, the corona pandemic is no more and no less than an example of the disruption of an existing balance between the overriding interests of a meta-organism and its defence strategies, be they reactive or proactive, and the interests and motives of an "enemy" acting asymmetrically "underground". The parallels to "system disrupters" are unmistakable, be it drug cartels, be it people who hide their "profits" in tax havens, be it from the perspective of democratically constituted societies an Islamic state or even a caliphate. This applies horrible dictu in general to "migration of the needy", whether individuals or larger groups, into other living spaces where they can develop at the expense of and in competition with the communities living there rather than where they come from. The process of urbanization, the migration into urban structures and into social systems that others have created for themselves, is in effect a pandemic. The resulting cultural conflict, which is spreading pandemically in our time, emerged along with the development of agriculture and cattle breeding, a way of life that has largely abandoned gathering and hunting and has given rise to the concept of property. This fundamental property thus created had to be defended against those who wanted to take it, secretly or by force. The idea of a divine creation, which should be freely accessible to all, and these newly created property rights, they clashed from then on. Even the holy writings of the Abrahamites still get lost morally and ethically in this dilemma between freedom and property. The attempt of the farmer Cain to defend his property against the shepherd Abel ends with Cain killing Abel, because his sacrifice was "more pleasing to God". Barriers against the access of third parties to „one's own" are indispensable for life in general. They do not only apply to humans, they apply to every cell and every organism. And the "army" that defends these barriers is called immune system. But in order to strengthen it, no general restrictions on "social contacts" will help. The immune system has to learn and it needs appropriate information about "the virus", which it can also get through vaccination.

The current very different curfews, travel restrictions and business closures can only delay the global spread of Covid-19, as they are incomplete by necessity due to the need of emergency supplies. Furthermore, the physical control of regional mobility and contact restrictions is a problem in itself. Police officers, doctors and medical staff also infect themselves despite some protective measures. These groups inevitably have an extremely high frequency of contact (Ong et al. 2020; Pung et al. 2020).

All the measures recommended by governments and health organizations are therefore only suitable for delaying a global spread of a pandemic with potentially fatal consequences for parts of very differently structured populations. They can slow down the speed of the

spread of the pandemic somewhat. But they cannot prevent different damage densities. This is because such measures depend on the sensitivity of complex supply structures, regardless of whether they are medical protection and treatment facilities or economically crucial production facilities. Modern societies do not simply depend on the provision of basic foodstuffs. They collapse if their complex, highly specialized exchange processes are sufficiently disrupted. To illustrate this in a picture: The individual human being does not die or a society does not collapse "from a virus", be it biological or mental, both cease to exist due to a disturbance of their internal organizational system triggered by a virus. And systems with an unstable internal organization, especially with serious information deficits, are particularly at risk.

Measures to limit "social contacts" to "the bare necessities" undoubtedly lead to a massive disruption of the world economy, which is now based on global supply chains. Their potentially much more dramatic longer-term consequences are largely ignored by efforts to give people a sense of „seriousness of the situation" at a time when only a tiny fraction of the population is infected. There is no doubt, however, that the virus has long since become much more widespread, as the infected individuals need a few days to sufficiently multiply the virus in their bodies before it becomes "contagious" and displays noticeable symptoms. Comprehensive tests are practically impossible, not only because of the lack of testing equipment, but also because of the intensive "social contacts" that are involved.

If one realizes that in modern societies based on specialization and a multiple division of labour, both the "supply chains" and the "intensity of demand" will probably remain disrupted for several months due to the reduction of social contacts to the bare minimum, then the upcoming second phase of the "confrontation with the corona virus" will have to deal with the economic consequences of revolutions or civil wars. After all, no economic or financial models are needed to ensure that the longer-term economic, psychological and then also political consequences triggered in this way cannot be contained by central banks printing empty money. The existing models are based on experience with disturbances that do not fundamentally question the structure of a highly interconnected global civilization.

The case of Corona and the political and social handling of it therefore raises the question of the reorganization of a global society. This materially and informally networked global society is coming up against several hard limits for many other reasons, which currently pushed aside. The problem of global "poverty migration", which has manifested itself in a similarly dramatic way for the public and politicians in 2015, is only one out of many. This is true for the "climate crisis", whose trigger is not only the "CO2 virus", but also for the "viruses" of population growth and the efforts to bring the "living standards" of the "poor" into line with those of the "rich" through a global redistribution and development effort - the deeper moral justification for the demand for permanent exponential growth. "Contagious" in general was and is the hope for a better life which, like viruses or bacteria, causes people to search for new "hosts" on a global scale.

The current situation makes it clear that the control of "pandemics" of any kind cannot be achieved through isolation, but only through targeted defensive measures, i.e. by

identifying parasitic behaviour as accurately as possible. Growth beyond a certain limit always turns into an uncontrolled proliferation of what is supposedly one's own, which ultimately destroys every organism and every organization.

In view of this situation, at a time when around 4 billion people, i.e. half of humanity, already own a smartphone, it seems overdue to examine this information and communication tool more closely in order to better understand how it contributes to the spread of all those "pandemics" mentioned above - and also how it could be used to combat them. For nationwide travel restrictions, and even more so, the restriction of individual freedoms in foreseeable increasing economic and social emergencies, questions the very order without which a civilization highly specialized and interlinked in a complex manner must collapse.

Without a targeted and coordinated limitation, indeed control, of physical and digital social contacts, neither the "migration" of viruses nor the "migration" of neediness will be controllable in the future.

Against this background, the essay *Legal Spaces and their Missing Digital Boundaries*, published already in 2018, is put up for discussion thereafter. It was written with a view to the necessary ordering and control of the digital information space, a phenomenon that is changing reality and whose significance we are only slowly becoming aware of. Perhaps the corona virus and the pandemic it has triggered will draw our attention in time to the inevitable changes in our traditional views of the world and of humanity and the values associated with them. To spread fears in order to influence the behaviour of the masses is highly risky. Surgical measures are necessary which must be determined by logic, but not by emotions. And such measures must be made understandable to the "common people", especially to specialists. Because ethical and moral discussions do not fight "viruses".

DIGITIZATION, GLOBALIZATION AND THE DISAPPEARANCE OF NATURAL "OPEN SPACES"

IN RECENT YEARS, MASS MIGRATION has become a social and political challenge in the developed countries of the West, but not only there. For the First World, it can in some respects be compared to the experience of those societies which after some time found themselves partially dispossessed, some even as slaves, of a process which "the West" has positively stored in its collective memory as emigration and occupation of new worlds with the help of superior techniques and a missionary spirit. The only real difference between current migration and the historical process of "emigration" is that current "immigration" uses the means of need instead of superior weapons and is based on the very belief that lies at the heart of Christian convictions: What you did to the least of my brothers, you did to me.

Political discussions how "the West" could meet this historical challenge break up existing political parties. They lead to surprising election results (Genç 2010, 186). They lead to surprising election results. And they not only upset the societies of Europe, they have even

reached the classic immigration country, the USA (Goodman and Schimmelfennig 2019). The events of 2015 have shown that the border regimes of the European Union are not simply deficient. The political conflicts triggered by irregular immigration are, if analyzed more closely, causally linked to the „desired“ economic globalization (Straubhaar and Zimmermann 1993, 230; Zorko 2018, 192, 196). This makes it so difficult both to assess the future development of migratory pressures and to develop a concept that would be free of contradictions in order to manage the overflowing "exchange" of goods, services, rules and finally always also people - and that means always to restrict them. It must be borne in mind that this "exchange" changes sources and sinks alike, and both already in a fundamental way.

There is no doubt, globalization has already passed the peak of its economic advantages. But this is not a widely shared consensus among economists (Colantone and Stanig 2019; Tagliapietra 2019). In their models they consider only those processes that are valued by markets (Hix and Noury 2007, 187, 190–191). An economy grows through a combination of different measures: through division of labour, development of easily accessible resources, spatial concentration and temporal acceleration of production and distribution processes, economies of scale, unification of standards and the deployment of increasingly complex technologies. The resulting "benefits", more precisely the "profits", are only incompletely recordable by monetary units, however. Not recorded, and not recordable in principle in economic sciences are, for example, changes in the natural environment, such as the consequences of climate change or the exhaustion of easy-to-use resources. Also not recorded is the depreciation of investments that are becoming obsolete by "progress", be it in the capital stock or in the "stock" of knowledge of productive people. It is not really surprising that with such an incomplete theoretical and vague approach politicians fail because the society they are supposed to lead and control is undergoing a profound transformation at a speed previously unimaginable (Küçüküsu 2019; McMillan 2003, 9).

A short-sighted policy aimed at combating symptoms wastes enormous resources. This is particularly true in the case of political decisions that are to be democratically legitimized. The administrative expenditure involved in organizing the redistribution of profits and losses from a rapidly changing production and consumption structure, i.e. the welfare state with all its intricate institutions and state "jobs" which are sprouting within it, generates costs which, similar to the elimination of accidents or environmental damage, are accounted as positive contributions to economic performance.

In view of the problems created by the "development" of societies, whether in the first, the second or third world, where whole states, and indeed regions, stagger into chaos and violence, the rapidly advancing pace of digitization is contributing to a further disparity between harsh reality and prevailing socio-economic theories. The catalysts for this schism between reality and theory this time is digital information processing and the digital communication coupled with it. The consequences of these digital communications, which are already visible today, seem to dwarf the consequences of the industrial revolution of the

19th and early 20th centuries in terms of both speed and structural change in societies that are groping in the dark.

There are first signs that a new social revolution is being sought by young "progressives", which, similar to what once Marx, then Lenin or later Mao kicked off, may lead to a collective excursion with dramatic consequences.³

Against this background, the memorandum "Securing national legal spaces" outlined a project for the technical establishment of borders in the digital space as early as 2016.⁴ The considerations contained therein, as well as the legal considerations put forward elsewhere as to whether and how a distinction should be made between those entitled to asylum, economic refugees, the immigration of qualified specialists, or even the compensation of demographic deficits, lead to a simple fact, namely that the migration of people cannot be controlled by national laws or international conventions, because these refer to rights of the individual, but not to mass phenomena. In this respect human migration is fundamentally different from the mass exchange of goods and services. For their "migration" is restricted by tariffs, by technical standards and also by financial institutions and rating agencies. **Economic globalization** does not aim at the freedom of individual people to move and settle where they like. Rather, it serves to establish an artificial technical living basis supported by different nations. In this respect, globalization aims at the establishment of globally anchored infrastructures and processes that are typical of mass production and mass supply. In its consequence, it **creates, unintentionally, a situation that does not differ substantially from the necessities and methods of livestock farming.** It is very difficult to even admit this.

MIGRATION AS A SYMPTOM OF GLOBAL HUMANITY

MIGRATION IS THEREFORE STILL UNDERSTOOD AS PART OF A MORE COMPREHENSIVE NATURAL RIGHT OF MAN, as a kind of elementary freedom, which also includes the exchange of convictions, of knowledge and even the direct access to a free "environment". This natural right referred to the physical and sensory reach of man, i.e. as far as the ears and eyes reach, as far as the environment can be manipulated by hands and as far as the feet carry. This elementary freedom of movement and the ability to act consciously, however, found its limits very early on as a result of the development of techniques that reached beyond the natural horizon of human perception. One does not shoot an arrow without being able to see the target. The risk of causing unwanted damage therefore limits every aspect of this

³ In the journal IPG (Internationale Politik und Gesellschaft) of 6.10.2017: *Windrädert doch wie wollt.*, Jason Hickel, an anthropologist at the London School of Economics, calls for »a fundamental economic turnaround, because renewable energies will and can no longer prevent the climate catastrophe.«

⁴ W. Sassin: Project proposal: Development of digital technologies for securing national legal spaces. 18.1.2016

natural right to freedom. But not only unknown risks, but also the necessity to form communities drastically limits the "freedom of movement and action". For only together can opportunities for living be expanded and secured that far exceed the abilities and possibilities of individuals. Communities must therefore limit the freedom of the individual for both reasons, because of the risks that grow with their size and because of the complexity of their cooperative undertakings. This double restriction of what we think we understand as a fundamental natural right, as freedom par excellence, increases disproportionately with the size of societies that have to artificially build, maintain and secure their livelihoods. At this point it should be noted that for 7.5 billion people there is simply no longer any possibility of a global relapse into the freedoms of nomadic or agricultural societies.

Against this background, the 10 points contained in the second section first list fundamental changes that characterize the gradual transition from highly diverse natural habitats with specifically adapted smaller societies to a universal, technically based basis for life. This new livelihood is no longer territorially restricted. It is provided by a **global urban culture** that has spread almost identically across all continents (Abel 2018; Martin 2016). This modern urban culture **is in principle not sustainable**. Firstly, it must be constantly renewed through human investment and is therefore **not a free, self-sustaining commons**. And secondly, it depends existentially on the exploitation of "its" flat land, further on the exploitation of the biosphere, the oceans, the atmosphere, and on natural material cycles, which can only buffer and process civilizational waste and pollutants to a limited extent.

A situation has arisen in which "migration" is a symptom but not the actual cause of the major current problems that are manifesting themselves in different forms in different societies.

Every living base developed by human beings is an existential property, the property of those who create this base. Global urban culture can therefore neither be appropriated through "immigration" nor by simply "being born into it", nor can it be adapted to traditional agricultural and nomadic cultural concepts.

In contrast to today's migration, earlier migratory movements led into free, still untouched natural areas. They forced "migrating" cultures to adapt to the highly diverse natural conditions. Migration today cannot be compared with the historical migrations of mankind, which can be traced back some 300,000 to 400,000 years. In any case, the original colonization of the planet has led to very specific characteristics of the individual and also to clearly distinguishable different cultures. De facto, at least half of homo sapiens has arrived on "another planet" in the course of the last century on which they cannot survive with their natural abilities. The fate of a species whose traditional values and sacred books do not guarantee a future is an obvious taboo of thought, especially for its fellow shamans and priests, including its lawyers and philosophers.

The current migratory flows, primarily from the countryside into highly dense urban areas and only in a second step from there "across borders" into "rich" urban societies, do not open up new horizons of civilization and also no new resources, as was still the case for

the settlement of the New World up to the 19th and early 20th century (Sassin et al. 2018, chap. 12).

For today's post-natural livelihoods, which have been lost through economic, but not through state or cultural expansion, migration is therefore always an act of partial expropriation, and above a certain "density of presence of migrants" it is even an unintentional, but unavoidable attack on the stability, indeed the existence of this modern urban culture.

The urban agglomerations with many millions of inhabitants that emerged in the second half of the 20th century, in which about half of the world's population now lives, differ only marginally from continent to continent. Their situation is similar to arks that are desperately searching for land that is not yet flooded or exploited because it is overcrowded.

The foreseeable worsening of the migration problem is therefore only a symptom of a much more general existential challenge that "man as a multi-billion phenomenon" is now facing. This challenge can best be described as the **Spaceship Earth problem**. Only in such a picture does it become clear that "the crew", i.e. the globalized society, must adapt to the limits caused by its growth, not the other way round. For these limits are by no means drawn by a changing climate or by depleted natural resources, but above all by the "neighbors" who are too close together, competing for space and resources, with their growing demands and their belief in supposed (natural) rights (Bonini Baldini 2019; Mazzucelli et al. 2016).

The implicit assumption that the existing, highly diverse cultures, their specific values and, viewed objectively, their archaic legal systems, could and must become part of a globally uniform legal space, not only questions all previous legal concepts. Above all, it unmasks the principles of interpersonal behaviour underlying these legal conceptions. It is important to remember that the "Western values" were born out of the revolt of the weak, who not only tried to disempower their high performers, but also to enslave them. The renewed striving for freedom that began after the experiences of the French Revolution and the attempted subjugation of an entire continent under Napoleon presupposes free spaces. It includes the claim for independence, for a break of the chains of inadequacy and the carrying along of social chains, whether they served to feed a self-appointed elite or the bottom of a society. The separation of the New England States from Britain (1776) and the creation of the American Constitution (1788) cannot be understood otherwise. The fact that "America" was a model for the problems of the 19th century, but is not suitable as a blueprint for the 21st century, simply follows from the fact that today we do not have a second New World at our disposal. The tradition enshrined in this constitution from two irreconcilable aspirations, namely the independence of self-defining communities and the simultaneous inner commitment of their individuals, is symbolically but but incompletely summarized in the United Nations catalogue of human rights.⁵

⁵ The group around George Washington did not have to resort to the guillotine simply because the nobles and successful entrepreneurs were sitting in England and not in their colonies in New England. Therefore, in order to achieve independence, firearms were sufficient to fight successfully against the

This catalogue therefore does not form a basis for a sustainable order in spaceship Earth. Its implicit values suppress and even deny, contrary to better knowledge, that rights can only result from the fulfillment of duties. The predominant and largely unconscious, but in any case naive idea of a further "moving together" for humanitarian reasons cannot compensate for any of the dramatic side effects of the global explosion of human needs and the economic growth driven by it, on the contrary. **The globalization of mankind is nothing less than the pursuit of a utopia for which – at least so far – no inherently consistent organizational model exists.**

IS THE EARTH TOO SMALL FOR THE NEEDS OF HUMANITY?

THE EARTH IS FINITE and after all that science has investigated so far, it is already too small for the demands of mankind. That means no less than: Man does not have to fundamentally change one technology or another but himself.

And above all: **the real challenge is not the absolute number of people who are connected or brought together, but their density in space and time, i.e. the density of communicative exchange processes that not only connect individuals but also constantly pressurize them and demand for control.**

If humanity as a whole would be organized as a global union, this would inevitably lead to a closed social system. In such a system, however, no different speeds in the adaption to performance standards can be tolerated. Nor could there be "markets" which balance supply and demand by price mechanisms and which, horrible dictu, accomplish a tacit distribution of scarcity. Moreover, such a closed social system could not allow for any significant tolerance for very different habits, i.e. what is taken for granted today in terms of personal freedom, including cultural and religious freedoms.⁶

colonial army of the British Crown. But they also killed there, but under martial law. A real revolution of the social order did not take place, unlike in France after the storming of the Bastille.

⁶ To understand the problems that the "humane idea" of integration and tolerance brings with it, it is enough to describe a real situation with unusual terms or as a seemingly bizarre process:

Traffic reports often warn of ghost drivers. These are drivers who are driving on motorways against the prescribed direction of travel. In countries like Germany with right-hand traffic, these are people who drive "left". If an Englishman, a Japanese or an Indian, i.e. people from countries with left-hand traffic, insisted that they must not only maintain their habits but also their now unconscious reactions in traffic in order to be really safe on the road, the consequence would be that ghost drivers in traffic would be the rule. In pedestrian traffic this is accepted, one could argue, i.e. in the dominant and still existing pre-technical form of movement. The integration of such an idea of natural freedom into a meticulously regulated high-tech society would then amount to the inevitable discrimination, indeed criminalization, of such "ghost drivers".

Not much different is the idea of introducing different holidays, with the help of which religions have so far distinguished themselves from each other with reference to different salvation histories, in

A *Spaceship Earth* can best be compared to the conditions in a besieged fortress. Without the possibility of external expansion, of shifting any kind of problem to the "outside", a free exchange of goods, of services and also the free movement of people inside this fortress would have to be drastically restricted and ultimately lead to a comprehensive planned economy. Such a system would dissolve all the requested basic freedoms of the individual, with the reasoning of a universal "social justice".

Meanwhile, a transformation is progressing rapidly towards a global planned economy, which has been taking place beneath the surface of public consciousness and for 70 years now propagated as *developing developing countries*. Digitization and with it the open information space that has only just come into being are accelerating this transformation in a so far unimaginable way. Like every newly discovered space, this additional "leeway" has so far known virtually no limits and certainly no internal structures.

Against the background of the evolving spaceship situation, or what amounts to the same, **the increasing idea of the One Humanity**, the establishment of effectively controllable boundaries in information space is one of the most urgent tasks. If this does not happen, mutiny and chaos will continue to spread throughout the spaceship.⁷

Digital borders not only represent an urgently needed means of limiting an expropriating migration, but they are also indispensable in the long run for the preservation of the technical and scientific basis of existence, especially from the perspective of the „weaker ones“. **How digital borders can be introduced in an information society without great effort to secure and stabilize legal spaces is outlined in Part 3 below. It refers to the fact that communication is always both the basis and the limitation of community.**

Without borders in the physical space and, in parallel, in the information space, markets as a means of improving economic efficiency would lose their function, because any progress of the economically successful would have to be redistributed by subsidizing the less successful. The supposed necessity for redistribution, which is enshrined in ideologically founded constitutions, even in the capitalist West, already destroys in reality the function of money as the central means of political control of larger societies. The growing indebt-

order to facilitate "integration" for cultural migrants. A modern economy in which there would be for example three "kinds of "sundays", namely the blessed Friday of the Mohammedans, the Sabbath of the Jews and the Sunday of the Christians would be just as efficient as a motorway with the individual freedom to drive left or right. Such examples can be continued at will. They show that the complexity of a system enforces a standardization of its constituent elements, and the more comprehensive the larger and more complex a system is. The humanities and social sciences, and even more so the political sciences, have yet to acquire this knowledge of the natural sciences.

⁷ Not only states in former colonial areas are disintegrating. Disintegration phenomena also occur in Europe. Scottish, Irish, Basque and Catalan attempts at autonomy, eastern Ukraine, Crimea, as well as the Brexit or the position of the Visegrad states in terms of immigration, are evidence of the instability and the inevitable disintegration of the EU. It is important to realize that the Soviet Union has also only recently disintegrated. In functional terms, this example is more interesting than the fall of the Roman Empire and is a warning sign for all the current major efforts to achieve union.

edness of states, companies and private citizens, which has been triggered by the global financial crisis after the beginning of this century, is one of the problems resulting from the process of "growing together" of differently developed economies. Single currencies such as the Euro force the need for "financing", i.e. nothing more than compensation for the performance deficits of individual members and groups. This is done either through taxes, which can only be increased to a limited extent, or through debts, which can be increased seemingly without limit and which can be extended almost indefinitely, especially over time. The ongoing process of globalization and digitalization is leading to ever new monetary aid programs. These are, however, ultimately just another term for "procurement rights", a means that every planned economy still had to introduce - and by which it necessarily must fail, sooner or later.

FUNDAMENTAL CHANGES AS A CONSEQUENCE OF SCIENTIFIC, TECHNOLOGICAL AND INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTIONS AND THEIR GLOBAL PROPAGATION

1. **LAW AND JUSTICE** always lag behind a new reality that has emerged before, and which they laboriously seek to put in order. Legal spaces presuppose states which autonomously establish law for their citizens and which make binding agreements for "their" legal subjects.

International law therefore refers either to territories for which states claim sovereign rights or to territories not under such sovereign rights, such as the oceans, Antarctica or near-Earth space including the Moon. The geological volumes below a very thin layer of the continents are so far free of rights, as is outer space. The same applies to the newly created *digital information space*.

To extend the right of a state to a foreign territory necessarily amounts to conquest or subjugation by military, economic and/or media means.

The process of subjugation of other legal systems took on unprecedented levels in the 20th century with the emergence of the duopoly US - Soviet Union and the subsequent establishment of global spheres of influence.

The "United Nations" and the human rights catalogues initiated thereby are the result of the attempt of two great powers to establish a coexistence between their fundamentally incompatible legal systems and the different concepts of humanity and the values they are based on after the end of the second, practically the first war waged worldwide.

Despite the disintegration of the Soviet Union and the hegemony of the USA, which arose for some time as a result, the United Nations has since then unilaterally pursued the goal of establishing a global legal regime, without really being able because of its existing structure to take proper account of the multipolarity that has developed in the meantime.

2. The "Ether" and the electromagnetic "long waves" spreading in it have first opened the possibility of a worldwide military command structure. Without the ether there could not have been a World War II. In fact the First *World War* was "only" a European war.

The "Ether" as a propagation medium for all kinds of electromagnetic waves is mentally not sufficiently recorded and classified regarding its military usability, legally not at all. As a "medium" for electromagnetic impulses it even opens up highly effective possibilities for the destruction of vital communication systems, for example by nuclear warheads that are detonated in near-Earth space and which can trigger a "magnetic pulse".

National standards exist in civilian areas, for example with regard to the intensity of certain high-energy radiation (X-rays and gamma radiation). There, influence is exerted on the sources.

3. International agreements on the 'use' of frequency bands have long existed to avoid interference with 'transmitters' and 'receivers' of electromagnetic waves. However, the existing standards for limiting the field strengths of electromagnetic waves only refer to their biological effects (similar problems as in point 2).

4. The information imprinted by humans on all sorts "carriers" and its distribution is and has never been free. The ability to control the distribution of information is the central instrument of extensive governance. With the emergence of non-material carriers of information, in particular electronic communication, legal restrictions on the "freedom of information" have developed, as well as technical measures by individual states to prevent undesired information transmission.

As long as the transmission of information was carried out by public agencies and there were only few such service providers, they were in practice monopolies which the State could actually control, both in terms of the content of the information and the technical means of transmission. (Censorship of the press, postal monopoly, state broadcasting, including state-operated jamming transmitters, and radio and telecommunications licences)

With the advent of mobile telephony, states on a large scale have privatized the technical transmission possibilities in return for massive taxation, arguing it would be a common resource comparable to mineral and other material public resources. (Auction of mobile radio frequency licenses) **Almost all countries have thus lost their sovereignty over mobile radio. The same applies to the digitally functioning Internet, which is a global network with distributed nodes.**

5. The transition from analogue to digital representation of information, in conjunction with the ARPA network developed for military purposes and the resulting commercial Internet, has created a situation in which de facto all states have lost control and protection of information transmission.

In fact, a largely ununderstood, fundamentally new global information space has developed in this way, which extends supranationally and to which almost everyone who wants to has anonymous access. (The parallels between graffiti sprayers and digital nerds are obvious. The former are extremely spatially limited in their activities, the latter almost not at all).

6. The deeper reason for the loss of control of the state over the information infrastructure is the yet non-existing concept of a *digital person in analogy to a natural and a legal person*. This failure creates existential problems for entire civilizations, not only for states, because of the development and the use of autonomously acting information processing programs. For the latter, too, there is no appropriate term. Because in the view in which mathematical-logical algorithms and their underlying models of the real world influence material or mental processes, a kind of **independently acting intelligence** is created. This intelligence, erroneously called "artificial", operates and communicates just like any natural person or legal entity in the information space. **The technical reproduction of neuronal networks and their connection with data volumes that can no longer be handled by humans, the so-called "deep learning", show that intelligence can also develop on other than biological substrates. However, these non-biological information and decision makers are not yet legal entities.**

7. With algorithms and the technical devices on which they are based, a new kind of "acting individuals" has emerged. But as long as these new digital individuals cannot be identified, similar to previous persons, whether natural or legal, they fundamentally evade any kind of law. (Here examples are: the existence of bots on the internet, which spread opinions or so-called fake news, as well as the influence of "foreign actors" on democratic election processes, but also the unsolved problem of legal responsibility for damages that autonomously driving vehicles will undoubtedly cause).

8. These new 'digital individuals' ultimately need to be registered as 'active citizens' if they are not to question every kind of legal system.

They could be called a special kind of "aliens". In disregard of their potential to make decisions independently of humans, we multiply them as if they were useful slaves who, like former slaves supposedly chained up, cannot cause harm. In fact, their owners let them act freely, at least in the information space, which can neither be "mapped" nor monitored and controlled by territorially bound legal systems. Our existential foundations depend more and more on the activity of these "aliens". The security problem that has already arisen and is getting worse and worse goes far beyond the known military threats. This is especially true with regard to nuclear weapons. A possible failure of larger parts of the electronic communication infrastructure caused by algorithms would lead to an unpredictable disintegration of modern, technically globalized civilization without even a single rocket being fired or a bomb being detonated (Sieferle 2016, 544f).

9. The obvious way to identify these new "intelligent citizens" is through their communication with their human owners and clients, i.e. natural and legal persons.

Human access to the information space always requires a physical "instrument", a mediating "something" between our neural networks, which produce our consciousness, and the environment, which cannot be physically captured, processed and stored, but only in the form of information.

In archaic cultures these were the voice and gestures, including facial expressions, which were used to exchange information. Not the content of the communication, but the voice

and face of an acting individual was always a public identification feature. They are unchanged. Later, writing was added. Handwriting, in conjunction with names and registers of persons, serves to identify citizens.

Since the advent of electric/electronic means of communication, starting with the telephone, telefax, radio, television, computers and smartphones, the possibilities of direct individual recognition of the communicating human actors have been lost.

The phenomenon of anonymization of information sources is widespread. It ranges from press officers and newsreaders to the "design" of journalistic reports and the alleged recording of reality by institutions that make use of statistics.

This also applies to the recording of information recipients, with the help of „audience rating“, or for effectiveness analyses of advertising and election campaigns.

After all, a growing number of state security agencies are busy identifying "unknown" listeners and readers of communication processes and content, such as those who "hack" IT devices, install Trojans and attempt to obtain "classified" information.

10. All communication beyond the natural range of the human sensory organs necessarily makes use of technical aids. The use of corresponding infrastructures is an economic process. For the purpose of settling claims arising from this, the telecommunication companies have customer directories. If these are linked to existing registers of residents, practically all actions that are triggered via the information space can be identified with the territorial position of the "digital agents", both the "sender" and the "receiver", and thus the client and the contractor of an action.

If this linkage is carried out by the state and not solely by private companies as has been the case to date, it would be possible to assign a legally binding identity to digital agents acting completely or partially autonomously. This would be similar to the allocation of a license plate for a motor vehicle, which does allow to identify the owner by the authorities. Even if a technical communications agent is located in a different legal area, a "holder" of a smartphone, for example, who is known to the state, it, or rather he could be held liable for the consequences of infringements of rights which are brought about with its help, even if the actual user cannot be identified directly.

What is decisive is that such a relatively simple administrative act can effectively protect the physical borders of a state. Of course, the free movement of such communication agents linked to the holder can be restricted just as easily as can the use of a vehicle registered in country A operating in in country B if the driver does not have a residence permit there.

PREREQUISITES FOR ORDERLY FURTHER DEVELOPMENT: COMMUNICATION AS THE BASIS AND THE LIMITATION OF SOCIETIES

ANY EQUIPMENT APPLICABLE FOR ELECTRONIC COMMUNICATION must be linked to the administrative and biometric data of its owner as a prerequisite for the use of public infrastructures. Only in this way can it be given an identity which, together with its owner, makes it a legally tangible subject.

Consistently implemented, this step would provide, among other things, an effective means of limiting cross-border migration and the associated violations of rights. In an electronically networked world, securing the rule of law is no longer conceivable in any other way. The advantage of such a measure would be to make physical border reinforcements and their physical monitoring and defence largely superfluous and to be able to transfer their task to electronic „guards“.

This requires smartphones and similar intelligent devices to be personalized and sooner or later take on the function of a passport or identity card. Technologies for many authentication processes have long been available on the market. So far, however, these only correspond to the issuing of private "passports" or commercial access rights, i.e. a kind of visa.

If the state were to provide smartphones and similar devices with sovereign "markings" and thus personalize them, then such intelligent communication devices that can be assigned to a foreign nationality could be excluded from the use of national communication infrastructures if their respective owners do not have legal residence status. This would not restrict any fundamental rights of the owner or holder of such an electronic communication device.

Such "personalization" of electronic communications should be clearly distinguished from monitoring or control of the content of communications. Rather, it is about the movement of a person in a territory for which that person does not have a visa or other legal residence permit, a fortiori to prevent the business of such persons in a particular territory. Actions of any kind using an electronic device, which is increasingly being used to remotely control installations and carry out transactions, in other words not just to "phone", ultimately corresponds to the establishment of a company, which must of course be entered in public registers and approved. A similar situation is emerging for autonomous vehicles that operate in different traffic systems, for example in countries with right-hand or left-hand traffic. The regulation of financial markets is another example.

The public connection data of identifiable electronic communication devices make it very easy to determine the origin of their owners and also the places where territorial and legal borders were crossed. It is precisely this information that was never considered to be private information when physical borders were crossed.

Here, the same applies to electronic communication as to previous analogue communication: the addressee on a simple letter and the indication of the sender cannot logically

be covered by the confidentiality of correspondence. Without them a letter could neither be transported nor delivered.

The elementary civilizational experiences of thousands of years must urgently be projected onto the electronic age and strictly applied to tame globalization. Without "smart" measures, the concepts of *state order and security to be guaranteed by the state* following the "privatization" of almost all communication infrastructures in recent decades will otherwise remain empty phrases.

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EXTENDED SUMMARY

SASSIN, WOLFGANG. GLOBALISATION AND DIGITISATION - THE EXPONENTIAL SPREAD OF INFECTIOUS INFORMATION AND ITS POSSIBLE CONTAINMENT.

THE CURRENT SPREAD OF A NEW CORONAVIRUS COVID-19 PANDEMIC, just as any other pandemic, demonstrates that we have an utmost need in establishing boundaries in otherwise truly global society. All of the measures recommended by governments and health organisations are not really suitable to prevent a pandemic, i.e. a global spread of a disease with potentially fatal consequences for parts of the population. At best, they can slow down the rate at which the pandemic spreads. In my work, I outline the basic principles of constructing a new possible ideology of digital limits that may prevent uncontrolled societal communication and,

therefore, slow down or even forestall the spread of infection in the world with almost eight billion people.

The implicit assumption that the existing, very different cultures, their special values and their objectively considered archaic legal systems could and should become part of a globally uniform legal area, not only questions all previous legal concepts. It exposes the underlying principles of interpersonal behaviour. "Western values" arose from the rebellion of the weak, who not only tried to disempower their top performers but to enslave them. After the experiences of the French Revolution and the attempt to subjugate an entire continent under Napoleon, the renewed striving for freedom presupposes free spaces. It includes the right to independence as well as to being free from the chains of inadequate and dragging along social chains. They served the alimentation of a self-proclaimed elite or the bottom of a society. The separation of the New England States from Britain (1776) and the establishment of the American Constitution (1788) cannot be understood otherwise. The fact that America was a model for exploring new spaces in the 19th century, but not a blueprint for such an activity in the 21st century, simply follows from the fact that we have no second New World available to us today.

Humanity understood as a whole, as a union organised globally, would inevitably lead to a closed social system. In such a system, there can be no different speeds in the adjustment of performance standards and no "markets" which allow a balance between supply and demand via price mechanisms. Furthermore, such a closed social system does would not show any appreciable tolerance towards highly different habits, i.e. what is taken for granted as personal freedoms, including cultural and religious freedoms. Digital borders are not only an urgently needed means of limiting expropriated migration, they are also essential to maintain the technical and scientific basis for existence, especially from the perspective of the "weaker".

I describe ten conditions necessary for the smooth transition from different natural living spaces to the universal life conditions upon new global technically-shaped Earth. Then I introduce the suggestion how to create and maintain digital borders without physical borders. If implemented consistently, this proposal would provide, among other things, an effective means of limiting uncontrolled cross-border migration – which is a symptom, not a cause of global society problems – and the related legal violations. In an electronically networked world, securing the rule of law is a not easy task. The advantage of such a measure would be to make physical border fortifications and their physical surveillance and defense largely superfluous and to be able to transfer their tasks to electronic "guards." This ideological measure is closely connected with reconsidering what we call digital freedom and digital identification in the global network.

The elementary civilisational experiences of millennia urgently need be projected onto the electronic age and used to tame globalisation. Without such measures, the terms "state order" and "security to be guaranteed by the state", after the "privatisation" of almost all communication infrastructures in the past decades, are otherwise just empty phrases.

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